

A Kinetic Study of Acid-catalysed Phloroglucinol-Acetophenone Reaction

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Kinetics of the reaction between phloroglucinol and acetophenone was investigated at different temperatures (30–45°) in methanol and different hydrochloric acid concentration (0.024–0.710M) were used. The reaction was promoted using thioglycolic acid (TGA) and the functionality of phloroglucinol was also taken into account. Reaction was found to obey second order kinetics. Activation parameters were calculated. The reaction was also carried out in solvents 1,4-dioxane, ethanol and methanol. The reactions were also carried out in presence of promoters thioglycolic acid and thiophenol. Overall rate constants were resolved into stepwise rate constants.

A review of literature reveals that comprehensive kinetic studies have been carried out on the phenols and substituted phenols-formaldehyde reactions¹⁻⁶, and phenol-ketone reactions^{7,8}. No kinetic study has been carried out on phloroglucinol-acetophenone reaction, taking into account the functionality of phloroglucinol. The reaction has been investigated at temperatures 30, 35, 40 and 45±0.05° and at hydrochloric acid concentrations of 0.024, 0.036, 0.051 and 0.071 M. The functionality of phloroglucinol has been taken into consideration while deriving various kinetic equations. To study the effect of promoter on the rate of the reaction, thioglycolic acid (TGA) and thiophenol (TP) have been employed as promoters.

Experimental

Phloroglucinol (E. Merck), acetophenone, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, NaOH (all B.D.H.) and methanol (Glaxo) were used. All other chemicals used were either of C.P. or A.R. grade. Phloroglucinol was recrystallised before use. An immersion type thermostat (German model NBE) was employed for the rate studies.

Method: Solutions of phloroglucinol and acetophenone of desired concentration were prepared in 100% methanol. Dry hydrochloric acid gas was bubbled for different time intervals through the acetophenone solution before use. The dissolved hydrochloric acid concentration was determined by mixing an aliquot of the solution in water and titrating against a standard solution of sodium hydroxide. The concentration of HCl was varied by adjusting the time interval for which hydrochloric acid gas was passed through the acetophenone solution. Reaction mixtures were obtained by mixing desired volume of acetophenone, phloroglucinol and thioglycolic acid solutions. The experiment was conducted in a closed system provided with stirring and reflux arrangement in a thermostat. The course of the reaction was followed

by estimating acetophenone by hydroxylamine hydrochloride method^{7,8} and phloroglucinol spectrophotometrically⁹ using diazotised *p*-nitroaniline as an indicator.

Results and Discussion

The results of the kinetic study are reported in Table 1. The overall reaction has been found to obey a second order rate law which conforms to that reported for phenol-acetone reaction⁷ and *o*-cresol-acetone reaction⁸ but differs from that observed in the phenol-acetone reaction¹⁰, to be third order.

A linear plot of $\log a/b[(b-y)/(a-1.91y)]$ vs time also confirms the reaction to be of second order. The various activation parameters for the overall reaction were obtained from transition state theory (Table 2). It has been observed that the energy of activation as well as entropy of activation decrease with increase in acid concentration confirming the role of H⁺ as catalyst.

Calculation of step wise rate constants: The reaction of phloroglucinol with acetophenone in acidic medium (low concentrations used) proceeds according to equations (i) and (ii),

The overall second order rate expression for the formation of product is

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a-x)(b-y) \quad (1)$$

where, *a* and *b* are the initial concentrations of phloroglucinol and acetophenone respectively, *x*

TABLE I—RESULTS OF KINETIC STUDY OF PHLOROGLUCINOL-ACETOPHONONE REACTION

[HCl] <i>M</i>	Initial [C ₆ H ₅ COCH ₃] <i>M</i>	Time s	[C ₆ H ₅ COCH ₃] reacted mol dm ⁻³	[Phloroglucinol] reacted mol dm ⁻³	Second order rate const. dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Average value of the rate constant dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹			
[Phloroglucinol]=0.4763 <i>M</i> , [Promoter]=0.004 <i>M</i> , Temp. = 30 ± 0.05°									
0.024	0.158	3 600	0.005 0	0.007 0	3.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	(3.33 ± 0.15) × 10 ⁻⁵			
		7 200	0.008 7	0.016 4	3.13 × 10 ⁻⁵				
		9 000	0.011 2	0.018 9	3.33 × 10 ⁻⁵				
0.036	0.157	13 200	0.016 2	0.029 4	3.36 × 10 ⁻⁵	(8.40 ± 0.16) × 10 ⁻⁵			
		3 600	0.011 3	0.019 3	8.47 × 10 ⁻⁵				
		7 260	0.023 8	0.047 1	8.60 × 10 ⁻⁵				
0.051	0.158	10 800	0.030 0	0.059 1	8.30 × 10 ⁻⁵	(1.37 ± 0.08) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		13 000	0.033 8	0.066 9	8.24 × 10 ⁻⁵				
		3 000	0.018 2	0.033 1	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.159	7 200	0.039 2	0.077 6	1.77 × 10 ⁻⁴	(4.52 ± 0.31) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		10 800	0.053 2	0.102 1	1.75 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		14 400	0.061 6	0.120 7	1.61 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.159	1 500	0.022 4	0.043 0	4.21 × 10 ⁻⁴	(4.52 ± 0.31) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		3 600	0.049 0	0.095 5	4.56 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		4 200	0.053 2	0.102 1	4.37 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.159	7 200	0.082 6	0.161 8	4.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	(4.52 ± 0.31) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		[Phloroglucinol]=0.4755 <i>M</i> , [Promoter]=0.004 <i>M</i> , Temp. = 35 ± 0.05°							
		0.024	0.157	5 400	0.013 5		0.026 2	6.71 × 10 ⁻⁵	(6.60 ± 0.20) × 10 ⁻⁵
7 200	0.017 5			0.033 7	6.75 × 10 ⁻⁵				
12 600	0.027 0			0.053 4	6.30 × 10 ⁻⁵				
0.036	0.156	14 400	0.032 4	0.064 1	6.64 × 10 ⁻⁵	(1.29 ± 0.19) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		3 600	0.019 8	0.036 6	1.36 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		9 000	0.033 0	0.062 9	1.11 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.051	0.157	12 600	0.046 2	0.089 0	1.23 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.55 ± 0.19) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		16 200	0.057 2	0.111 9	1.29 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		3 600	0.031 9	0.059 9	2.70 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	7 200	0.055 0	0.105 5	2.72 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.55 ± 0.19) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		12 600	0.071 5	0.139 4	2.31 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		15 300	0.083 6	0.163 7	2.48 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	1 200	0.026 0	0.050 7	6.38 × 10 ⁻⁴	(6.24 ± 0.10) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		2 400	0.045 4	0.089 3	6.24 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		3 600	0.060 5	0.117 0	6.15 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	6 300	0.085 2	0.168 6	6.19 × 10 ⁻⁴	(6.24 ± 0.10) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		[Phloroglucinol]=0.4759 <i>M</i> , [Promoter]=0.004 <i>M</i> , Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°							
		0.024	0.159	3 600	0.017 6		0.031 5	1.34 × 10 ⁻⁴	(1.46 ± 0.11) × 10 ⁻⁴
7 200	0.033 8			0.064 8	1.40 × 10 ⁻⁴				
11 700	0.055 4			0.108 4	1.60 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.036	0.157	14 400	0.062 1	0.122 3	1.52 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.43 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		3 000	0.025 6	0.047 8	2.49 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		7 200	0.051 3	0.099 9	2.46 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.051	0.158	10 800	0.067 5	0.133 0	2.44 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.43 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		14 400	0.079 6	0.157 6	2.33 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		1 800	0.021 9	0.042 4	3.45 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.157	3 600	0.043 7	0.084 7	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	(3.54 ± 0.25) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		6 600	0.061 0	0.120 1	3.41 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		1 800	0.084 0	0.156 3	3.49 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.157	900	0.021 8	0.042 5	6.91 × 10 ⁻⁴	(7.02 ± 0.08) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		2 400	0.049 4	0.097 3	7.01 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		3 540	0.065 5	0.127 7	7.06 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.157	5 400	0.085 1	0.163 3	7.06 × 10 ⁻⁴	(7.02 ± 0.08) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		[Phloroglucinol]=0.4762 <i>M</i> , [Promoter]=0.004 <i>M</i> , Temp. = 45 ± 0.05°							
		0.024	0.158	3 540	0.032 7		0.062 2	2.80 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.83 ± 0.09) × 10 ⁻⁴
6 600	0.055 5			0.108 9	2.97 × 10 ⁻⁴				
7 900	0.069 8			0.137 6	2.75 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.036	0.156	12 600	0.081 2	0.160 9	2.83 × 10 ⁻⁴	(3.70 ± 0.23) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		3 600	0.041 2	0.077 8	3.72 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		6 600	0.059 8	0.112 4	3.36 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.051	0.157	7 200	0.069 8	0.133 3	3.85 × 10 ⁻⁴	(3.70 ± 0.23) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		9 900	0.084 1	0.163 1	3.87 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		1 800	0.030 8	0.059 1	5.14 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	3 600	0.050 5	0.078 4	4.81 × 10 ⁻⁴	(5.06 ± 0.16) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		4 200	0.059 4	0.115 2	5.17 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		6 400	0.077 0	0.150 9	5.13 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	1 800	0.047 3	0.093 1	8.64 × 10 ⁻⁴	(8.63 ± 0.16) × 10 ⁻⁴			
		2 700	0.062 7	0.124 1	8.55 × 10 ⁻⁴				
		3 600	0.077 0	0.151 6	8.87 × 10 ⁻⁴				
0.071	0.158	4 800	0.088 0	0.174 4	8.48 × 10 ⁻⁴	(8.63 ± 0.16) × 10 ⁻⁴			

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR PHLOROGLUCINOL ACETOPHENONE REACTION

[HCl] M	ΔE^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
0.024	30.40	+22.53
0.036	22.85	-2.03
0.051	15.99	-23.04
0.071	9.89	-41.18

and y are the amounts of phloroglucinol and acetophenone reacted respectively in time t .

From equations (i) and (ii) it is obvious that phloroglucinol is being used in both the steps. Therefore, at any stage in the reaction the amount of the phloroglucinol consumed will be more than that of acetophenone. This can be verified from the results (Table 1). The average proportion of phloroglucinol and acetophenone reacted is actually found to be $x = 1.91y$. Substituting the values of x in equation (1) and on integration we get expression for the overall rate constant,

$$k = \frac{2.303 \times 1.91}{t(1.91b-a)} \log \frac{a}{b} \left(\frac{b-y}{a-1.91y} \right) \quad (2)$$

From equations (i) and (ii), the rate of formation of the alcohols, 2-(1-phenyl-1-methylmethan-1-ol)-3,5-dihydroxy phenol is

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = k_1(na-y-r)(b-y) \quad (3)$$

where $(b-y)$ and $(na-y-r)$ are the concentrations of acetophenone and phloroglucinol left at time t and n is the functionality of phloroglucinol.

The rate of formation of 2,2'-(1-phenyl-1-methylmethane)bis(3,5-dihydroxyphenol) is

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = k_2(na-y-r)(y-r) \quad (4)$$

$(na-y-r)$ is the concentration of phloroglucinol at time t . The amount of phloroglucinol reacted at any stage of the reaction is equal to the sum of the amount of acetophenone and tert-alcohols, 2-(1-phenyl-1-methylmethan-1-ol)-3,5-dihydroxyphenol reacted at any time t ,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dy}{dt} + \frac{dr}{dt} \quad (5)$$

From equations (3), (4) and (5),

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = nk_1(a-x)(b-y) + nk_2(a-x)(y-r) \quad (6)$$

From equations (1) and (6),

$$k(a-x)(b-y) = nk_1(a-x)(b-y) + nk_2(a-x)(y-r) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or } k = nk_1 + nk_2 \left(\frac{y-r}{b-y} \right) \quad (8)$$

Now, $(y+r) = x$, or $r = (x-y)$ and the functionality of phloroglucinol $n=1$.

$$\text{Therefore, } k = k_1 + k_2 \left(\frac{2y-x}{b-y} \right) \quad (9)$$

Substituting the values of x , y and k (from Table 1) at two different time intervals, two simultaneous equations for k_1 and k_2 at a given temperature and HCl concentration are obtained. These equations are then solved for k_1 and k_2 , and is reported in Table 3. As is clear from Table 3, the rate of formation 2,2'-(1-phenyl-1-methylmethane)bis(3,5-dihydroxyphenol) is 46–47 times the rate of formation of tertiary alcohol, i.e. $k_2/k_1 = 46 \approx 47$.

TABLE 3—STEPWISE RATE CONSTANT AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND [HCl]

[HCl] M	k_1 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k_2 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	k_2/k_1 $= \mu$
Temp. = 30 ± 0.05°			
0.024	1.73 × 10 ⁻⁵	8.19 × 10 ⁻⁴	47.34
0.036	4.03 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.91 × 10 ⁻³	46.69
0.051	8.19 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.88 × 10 ⁻³	47.37
0.071	1.54 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.38 × 10 ⁻³	47.92
Temp. = 35 ± 0.05°			
0.024	4.23 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.00 × 10 ⁻³	47.28
0.036	6.86 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.16 × 10 ⁻³	46.06
0.051	1.06 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.96 × 10 ⁻³	46.79
0.071	2.13 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.01 × 10 ⁻²	47.41
Temp. = 40 ± 0.05°			
0.024	6.51 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.11 × 10 ⁻³	47.77
0.036	1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.13 × 10 ⁻³	47.06
0.051	1.69 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.07 × 10 ⁻³	47.75
0.071	2.68 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.24 × 10 ⁻²	46.26
Temp. = 45 ± 0.05°			
0.024	1.20 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.68 × 10 ⁻³	47.33
0.036	1.29 × 10 ⁻⁴	6.01 × 10 ⁻³	46.58
0.051	1.87 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.70 × 10 ⁻³	46.52
0.071	3.61 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.71 × 10 ⁻²	47.36

TABLE 4—COMPARISON OF OVERALL RATE CONSTANT

Temp. ±0.05°C	[HCl] M	Average value of overall rate constant (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	
		Experimental eqn. (2)	Theoretical eqn. (10)
35	0.036 8	1.29 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.89 × 10 ⁻⁴
45	0.024 3	2.83 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.41 × 10 ⁻⁴

The second order rate expression has been confirmed by making a comparison of the values of the overall rate constant obtained using equation (2) with the overall rate constant values as obtained purely from theoretical consideration of the reaction by using equation (10)⁸ (Table 4),

$$k = k_1 + \frac{k_2}{\mu - 1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{b-y}{b} \right)^{\mu - 1} \right] \quad (10)$$

Kinetic investigation has also been carried out in presence of promoters thioglycolic acid (TGA) and thiophenol (TP) and in the absence of a promoter at 40 ± 0.05° and 0.0710 M concentration. Rate constants have been compared in Table 5. Reaction rate varies in the following manner: TGA > TP > without promoter. This behaviour can be explained on the basis of the following arguments that in the presence of H⁺ ions, TGA and

TP form the intermediate hemithioketals 1 and 2 respectively.

These hemithioketals (1 and 2) generate thioglycollate ion and thiophenolate ion respectively in the presence of H^+ which further react with acetophenone to form carbonium ion 3 regenerating the thioglycollate and thiophenolate ions. When the reaction is taking place in the absence of the promoter the production of the carbonium ion is much less, therefore, the reaction carried out using promoter is much faster.

The reaction has also been carried out at temperature $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and 0.0510 M in HCl using 1,4-dioxane, ethanol and methanol as solvents (Table 6). Rate of the reaction is found to vary in the following manner: 1,4-dioxane > ethanol > methanol. Such a behaviour is in agreement with the fact that the reaction rate decreases in presence of water molecule. Solvent being most polar, will absorb maximum number of water molecules. With the decrease in polarity of the solvent, rate of the

reaction increases. However, polarity of the solvent decreases with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (methanol, 32.6; ethanol, 24.3; 1,4-dioxane, 2.204 at 25°).

Scheme 1

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF RATE CONSTANT IN PRESENCE OF PROMOTERS AND WITHOUT PROMOTERS

Temp. = $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$, $[\text{HCl}] = 0.0710 \text{ M}$						
Initial $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3]$ <i>b</i> (M)	Initial phloroglucinol <i>a</i> (M)	Time s	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3]$ reacted mol dm^{-3}	[Phloroglucinol] reacted mol dm^{-3}	Second order rate constant $\times 10^{-4}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Average value of rate constant $\times 10^{-4}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Without promoter						
0.156 7	0.474 8	1 800	0.017 1	0.032 6	3.09	3.12 ± 0.08
		3 600	0.037 0	0.071 0	3.24	
		7 200	0.061 3	0.117 0	3.03	
		12 000	0.084 1	0.160 6	3.15	
[Thioglycollic acid] = 0.004 M						
0.157 5	0.475 9	900	0.021 8	0.042 5	6.91	7.02 ± 0.08
		2 400	0.049 4	0.097 3	7.01	
		3 540	0.065 5	0.127 7	7.06	
		5 400	0.085 1	0.163 3	7.11	
[Thiophenol] = 0.004 M						
0.167 5	0.475 8	3 000	0.042 8	0.080 8	4.60	4.44 ± 0.10
		5 400	0.063 0	0.119 7	4.42	
		6 600	0.072 0	0.136 8	4.37	
		9 000	0.086 0	0.163 3	4.40	

TABLE 6—REACTION CARRIED OUT IN VARIOUS ORGANIC SOLVENTS

[Promoter] = 0.004 M, $[\text{HCl}] = 0.0510 \text{ M}$, Temp. = $35 \pm 0.05^\circ$							
Solvent	Time s	Initial $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3]$ M	Initial [Phloroglucinol] M	$[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3]$ reacted mol dm^{-3}	[Phloroglucinol] reacted mol dm^{-3}	Second order rate const. $\times 10^{-4}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	Average rate const. $\times 10^{-4}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
1,4-Dioxane	1 800	0.157	0.475	0.025 2	0.048 1	4.63	4.48 ± 0.14
	3 600			0.043 1	0.082 9	4.44	
	7 200			0.072 0	0.136 1	4.56	
	9 000			0.079 8	0.153 2	4.30	
Ethanol	3 303	0.159	0.479	0.033 3	0.062 3	3.03	3.01 ± 0.05
	4 500			0.043 5	0.083 0	3.07	
	7 200			0.059 8	0.115 5	2.93	
	10 800			0.080 8	0.154 3	3.02	
Methanol	3 600	0.157	0.475	0.031 9	0.059 9	2.70	2.55 ± 0.19
	7 200			0.055 0	0.105 5	2.72	
	12 600			0.071 5	0.139 4	2.31	
	15 300			0.083 6	0.163 7	2.48	

Mechanism : In case of phloroglucinol, due to inductive and mesomeric effect, the electron density is greater at *ortho*- and *para*-positions as compared to *meta*-position. Therefore, phloroglucinol acquires a negative charge at these positions. Therefore, carbonium ion 3 attacks the *ortho*-position to form the activated complex 4 (Scheme 1). The formation of 4 is a slow reaction and is rate-determining. The activated complex will quickly form a stable compound the tert-alcohols, 2-(1-phenyl-1-methylmethan-1-ol)-3,5 dihydroxyphenol (5). Compound 5 rearranges to form a carbonium ion 6 in the presence of H⁺ ion. The carbonium ion 6 condenses with a molecule of phloroglucinol to form the final product (7).

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